

Hubble constant estimation from BAO signals with LSST-simulated data

M. A. Sabogal,^{a,1} J. E. Gonzalez,^b

^aPrograma de Física, Universidad del Atlántico, Carrera 30 Número 8-49, Puerto Colombia-Atlántico, Colombia

^bDepartamento de Física, Universidade Federal de Sergipe, Aracaju, SE 49100-000, Brazil

E-mail: msabogal@est.uniatlantico.edu.co, javiergonzalezs@academico.ufs.br

Abstract. One of the most important puzzles of the current cosmological scenario is the tension between the model-independent estimate of the Hubble constant (H_0) from Cepheids /Supernovae-Ia and the value inferred from the Cosmic Background Radiation (CMB) fluctuations assuming the Λ CDM model. A promising method to obtain evidence in favor of one of these values is to use non-parametric regressions to estimate the expansion rate of the universe at $z = 0$. The present project developed during the RECA Internship program 2022 consisted in applying the non-parametric reconstruction method known as Gaussian Processes to the simulated anisotropic BAO signals, to obtain an estimate of the uncertainty of H_0 in a future BAO measurement performed by the LSST.

¹Corresponding author: msabogal@est.uniatlantico.edu.co

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Gaussian Processes	2
3	Data and Methodology	3
4	Results and discussion	6
5	Conclusions	11

1 Introduction

Cosmological research throughout history has led us to the current standard cosmological model, the Λ CDM, in which CDM is the cold dark matter and Λ corresponds to the cosmological constant, which is the simplest candidate to represent the dark energy that causes the accelerated expansion of the universe as indicated by several astronomical observations [1–5]. However, the strong advance in the precision of cosmology, and despite being consistent with current cosmological data, has unveiled that Λ CDM has inconsistencies such as the fitting problem [6], the coincidence problem [7] and the tension in the current value of the Hubble parameter (H_0). In this regard, numerous alternative cosmological models have been proposed in the literature that can explain the data and also have some convincing theory [8, 9]. The most relevant observational issue is the current tension on the H_0 parameter. Assuming the Λ CDM model, the analysis of the data from Planck-CMB suggests a value of $H_0 = 67.4^{+0.5}_{-0.5}$ km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹ [10], while the combination of the model-independent local measurements yields $H_0 = 73.3^{+0.8}_{-0.8}$ km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹ [11], which it is in a tension of 5.8σ with CMB constraints.

One of the many physical phenomena that allow estimating the value of H_0 are the acoustic oscillations of the Baryons, which were generated when in the tightly coupled photon-plasma fluid before recombination, the acoustic waves, supported by the photon pressure, created a characteristic scale known as the Sound Horizon (R_S) in the fluid distribution [12]. Subsequent to decoupling, the sound horizon ‘frozen’ but continued to evolve gravitationally in the matter distribution and in the subsequent correlation functions of galaxies [13]. The sound horizon during recombination can be precisely determined with the CMB, so BAO becomes a very important standard rule for measuring the angular diameter distance, comoving distance, and the Hubble parameter [14].

As mentioned before, theoretical models are proposed in the literature to study cosmology beyond Λ CDM. While this approach may provide tight constraints on the cosmological parameters, the results may be biased towards the models considered [15]. An interesting and robust alternative is to consider a Gaussian process (GP) [16] to reconstruct the cosmological parameters in a model-independent way, a method that has become especially popular in the last decade [17–23]. In this work, we want to apply the non-parametric reconstruction method GP to the simulated anisotropic BAO signals from the LSST, to obtain an estimate

of the H_0 uncertainty in a future BAO measurement performed by the LSST.

The manuscript is organised as follows. In Section 2 we set our notation and the GP framework. In Sections 3 we present the data sets used in this work and the methodology used. In Section 4 we present and discuss our results. Finally, in Section 5 we give our conclusions.

2 Gaussian Processes

Gaussian processes (GP) are a fully Bayesian analysis describing a distribution over functions, and are therefore a generalization of Gaussian distributions to function space. A GP allows to perform the reconstruction of a function from the data, without assuming a parameterization of the function. Given a data set D of n observations:

$$\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i) \mid i = 1, \dots, n\} , \quad (2.1)$$

as mentioned before the main idea is to reconstruct a function $f(x)$ that describes the data. In this paper we will follow the notation in [17], so we will write the training input set, i.e., the locations $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$ of the observations, as \mathbf{X} , and the locations at which we want to reconstruct the function are denoted as \mathbf{X}^* . A Gaussian process can be written as

$$f(x) \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mu(x), k(x, \tilde{x})) , \quad (2.2)$$

where the value of f when evaluated at a point x is a Gaussian random variable with mean $\mu(x)$ and the variance is related to the covariance function $\text{cov}(f(x), f(\tilde{x})) = k(x, \tilde{x})$. There is a wide range of possible covariance functions [16]. Throughout this work, unless said otherwise, we use the squared exponential covariance function:

$$k(x, \tilde{x}) = \sigma_f^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \tilde{x})^2}{2\ell^2}\right) . \quad (2.3)$$

The function on Eq. (2.3) has the advantage that it is infinitely differentiable, which is useful for reconstructing the derivative of a function. This function depends on the two ‘hyperparameters’ σ_f and ℓ , which characterize the ‘bumpiness’ of the function. The characteristic length scale ℓ is described in the literature as the distance one has to travel in x -direction to get a significant change in $f(x)$, whereas the signal variance σ_f denotes the typical change in the y -direction [17].

One can generate a Gaussian vector \mathbf{f}^* of function values at \mathbf{X}^* with $f_i^* = f(x_i^*)$ and observational data \mathcal{D} can also be described by a Gaussian process \mathbf{y} . Where the covariance matrix C of the data has to be added to the covariance matrix $[K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})]_{ij} = k(x_i, x_j)$. Assuming the errors are Gaussian with variance σ_i^2 and for uncorrelated data we have simply $C = \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2)$. Therefore, the two Gaussian processes for \mathbf{f}^* and \mathbf{y} can be combined in the joint distribution:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y} \\ \mathbf{f}^* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\mu} \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + C & K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^*) \\ K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) & K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}^*) \end{bmatrix}\right) , \quad (2.4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}^*$ is the a priori assumed mean of \mathbf{f}^* . The notation \mathcal{N} means the Gaussian process \mathcal{GP} is evaluated at specific points x^* , where $f(x^*)$ is a random value drawn from a normal

distribution. While \mathbf{y} is known from observations, we want to reconstruct \mathbf{f}^* . This can be done with the conditional distribution by obtaining the expressions (see the Appendix in [17]):

$$\mathbf{f}^* | \mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{y} \sim \mathcal{N}(\overline{\mathbf{f}^*}, \text{cov}(\mathbf{f}^*)) , \quad (2.5)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{f}^*}$ is the mean given by:

$$\overline{\mathbf{f}^*} = \boldsymbol{\mu}^* + K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + C]^{-1}(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}), \quad (2.6)$$

and $\text{cov}(\mathbf{f}^*)$ is the covariance of Eq. (2.5), know as the posterior distribution,

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{f}^*) = K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}^*) - K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + C]^{-1} K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^*) . \quad (2.7)$$

As the reader can probably guess, the hyperparameters σ_f and ℓ still need to be known. They can be trained by maximizing the marginal likelihood, which is the marginalization over function values \mathbf{f} at locations \mathbf{X} , define as:

$$p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{X}, \sigma_f, \ell) = \int p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{X}) p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{X}, \sigma_f, \ell) d\mathbf{f} . \quad (2.8)$$

With a Gaussian prior $\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{X}, \sigma_f, \ell \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}))$ and with $\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{f} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{f}, C)$, the integration of Eq. (2.8) yields the log marginal likelihood:

$$\ln \mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + C]^{-1}(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}) - \frac{1}{2} \ln |K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + C| - \frac{n}{2} \ln 2\pi , \quad (2.9)$$

where it is important to point out that $\mathcal{L} = p(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{X}, \sigma_f, \ell)$ only depends on the locations \mathbf{X} of the observations, but not on the points \mathbf{X}^* , where we want to reconstruct the function. Now the hyperparameters can be found by maximizing Eq. (2.9) or marginalized over them using MCMC methods. Gaussian Processes are a quite powerful method because it can also be used to reconstruct the derivatives of $f(x)$ since the derivative of a Gaussian process is again a Gaussian process [16],

$$f'(x) \sim \mathcal{GP} \left(\mu'(x), \frac{\partial^2 k(x, \tilde{x})}{\partial x \partial \tilde{x}} \right) , \quad (2.10)$$

and the hyperparameters are trained in the same way as for the reconstruction of $f(x)$ since the marginal likelihood in Eq. (2.9) that has to be maximized only depends on the observations, but not on the function we want to reconstruct.

3 Data and Methodology

To estimate the uncertainty of H_0 in a future BAO measurement by the LSST, two libraries were built based on the widely used `GaPP` code [17], where the comoving distance $D(z)$ and its derivative are reconstructed from the independent data sets in [24] and [25], in order to obtain $H(z)$.

Firstly, we perform an analysis with the `Analysis GP` library (as described in Figure 1) where Eq. (2.9) is maximized to determine the hyperparameters. The fiducial model to simulate our universe can be chosen among the options Λ CDM, w CDM or the Granda-Oliveros holographic dark energy model (GO) [26], being LCDM the default model. Secondly, an analysis with the `Analysis GP-MCMC` library (as described in the Figure 2) where a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) statistical analysis is performed by sampling the hyperparameter space $\theta = \{\sigma_f, \ell, \Omega_{m_0}, H_0\}$ with the `emcee` code [27].

Figure 1. Description of the process performed by the *Analysis GP* library: Firstly, the combined LSST data set is imported (upper left box), which consist of redshift z values with their corresponding estimate error of $D(z)$ from the BAO signals. The possible future measurement of $D(z)$ is simulated N times in a Gaussian random way, taking as mean value the fiducial model $D^*(z)$ at a certain value of z and the variance as the corresponding error estimate of the LSST data at that value of z . Secondly, after setting the initial conditions (upper right box), the N reconstructions of the simulated data sets are performed, obtaining $D(z)$, $D'(z)$ and their uncertainty. Through the relation between D' and H we obtain the N reconstructed $H(z)$ functions and their uncertainties. Finally, for each value of z^* (redshift at which the reconstruction was performed) of the N reconstructions, a Gaussian random sampling of N^* values is performed, taking as mean value the corresponding values of $H^*(z)$ and their uncertainty as variance. Then the samples corresponding to each value of z^* are concatenated and the average and standard deviation are obtained, with special attention to $z = 0.0$

Figure 2. As in Analysis GP, the process in Analysis GP-MCMC library imports the LSST data, but simulates only a random set of value based on the fiducial model. This set of value is used for the MCMC, from which N chains of hyperparameters $\theta = \{\sigma_f, \ell, \Omega_{m_0}, H_0\}$ are selected that must be within 5σ of the mean values found. From the N chains with fixed θ , N reconstructions are performed, and the process continues and ends as in Figure 1.

4 Results and discussion

For the first part of our analysis we use the LSST data set and methodology described in Figure 1 with $N = 100$, $N^* = 1000$ and $\mu = 0$. In the first instance we study the case with Λ CDM as the fiducial model (Figure 3).

Figure 3. With the Λ CDM as fiducial model (Left) N reconstructions of $H(z)$ from the simulated data [24, 25]. (Right) Final estimation of $H(z)$ values (blue solid line) and their uncertainty (light blue region), in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

In the Figure 3 on the left we can observe how the N reconstructions behave especially at $z=0$ and on the right the final reconstruction of $H(z)$. We can also observe in the upper right side of Figure 3 that the H_0 estimation coincides within 1σ of confidence with the value set for this simulated universe.

Secondly, we consider w CDM and GO as fiducial models in Figures 4 and 5 respectively. Finding that by the method of the optimization of Eq. (2.9) the best results obtained are when Λ CDM is considered as the fiducial model, which was expected, since is well-known Λ CDM is the current model that best represents the observations. However, it should be noted that in all cases the value of H_0 is recovered, unveiling the robustness of the methodology used.

Next we explain the second part of our analysis where will be taken GO as the fiducial model and Λ CDM as the prior mean function. Instead of optimizing Eq. (2.9) we studied the hyperparameter space using MCMC as described in Figure 2. In the output chains by Analysis GP-MCMC, it can be seen in Figure 6 how Ω_{m_0} and H_0 converge in the region where the "real" values are found for this simulated universe, while it is evident that there is no preference for the value of ℓ and σ_f prefers values close to zero.

Figure 4. With the w CDM as fiducial model (Left) N reconstructions of $H(z)$ from the simulated data [24, 25]. (Right) Final estimation of $H(z)$ values (blue solid line) and their uncertainty (light blue region), in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

Figure 5. With the GO as fiducial model (Left) N reconstructions of $H(z)$ from the simulated data [24, 25]. (Right) Final estimation of $H(z)$ values (blue solid line) and their uncertainty (light blue region), in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

Figure 6. MCMC chains for the hyperparameters in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

The probability contours on Figure 8 illustrate the relationship between the hyperparameters and the confidence intervals at 1σ , 2σ and 3σ , highlighting even better the behaviors observed in Figure 6 in agreement with what has been recently reported in the literature [15].

An interesting aspect of our analysis arises when we compare the reconstructions obtained by optimization versus those obtained by marginalization. While the reconstructions by the marginalization method perform well as z increases, the reconstructions by optimization do not, their error bars increase as we move into the past [28]. Therefore, the marginalization method has a higher range of accuracy.

Figure 7. Probability contours of the hyperparameters in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

Finally, our results for the reconstruction of $H(z)$ using the **Analysis GP-MCMC** method are shown in Figure 9, where it is evident in the left figure that despite exhibiting a wider dispersion between the N reconstructions compared to Figure 3, the behavior of the functions is smoother and more uniform in $z = 0$, as in the final reconstruction in the right figure, which is reflected in lower uncertainty values, as shown in the upper part of the right figure.

Figure 8. Comparison of the reconstruction of $H(z)$ (blue solid line) and its uncertainty (light blue region) by the Optimization (Left) and Marginalization (Right) methods, in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

Figure 9. By marginalization with the Λ CDM as prior mean function (Left) N reconstructions of $H(z)$ from the simulated data [24, 25]. (Right) Final estimation of $H(z)$ values (blue solid line) and their uncertainty (light blue region), in a simulated universe with $\Omega_{m_0} = 0.3$ and $H_0 = 70.0$.

5 Conclusions

In this work we tested the possibility of applying the non-parametric reconstruction method known as Gaussian Processes [17] to the simulated BAO signals [24, 25]. From which we can conclude the reconstructions with the optimized hyperparameters have higher confidence levels in H_0 . These results show that the optimization approach significantly overestimates the errors by not including other combinations that still give a good fit to the data, which are included in the MCMC marginalization approach. We also found no preference for ℓ in the marginal probability distribution with the mean prior function as Λ CDM. When the derivative is reconstructed with the optimization method, large error bars will be obtained at higher values of z , however, with the marginalization approach this problem is solved. Since Λ CDM is a ‘good enough’ description of the data, **Analysis GP** does not find preference for deviations, and the marginal probability distribution peaks at small values of σ_f , as recently reported in [15]. Last but not most important, from the simulated LSST data, the H_0 uncertainty in a future LSST measurement of BAO is estimated to have a value of $\sigma = 0.8$, allowing to differentiate between the current tension values up to 5σ of confidence.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the RECA Internship program 2022 and the LSST observatory.

Numerical codes

Modified **GaPP** code reproducing results in this work can be found in the repository **ModifyGaPP**.

References

- [1] A. G. Riess, A. V. Filippenko, P. Challis, A. Clocchiatti, A. Diercks, P. M. Garnavich et al., *Observational evidence from supernovae for an accelerating universe and a cosmological constant*, *The Astronomical Journal* **116** (1998) 1009.
- [2] G. Aldering, S. Perlmutter, R. Knop, P. Nugent, G. Goldhaber, D. Groom et al., *Measurements of omega and lambda from high-redshift supernovae*, in *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, vol. 193, pp. 39–04, 1998.
- [3] S. Alam, M. Ata, S. Bailey, F. Beutler, D. Bizyaev, J. A. Blazek et al., *The clustering of galaxies in the completed sdss-iii baryon oscillation spectroscopic survey: cosmological analysis of the dr12 galaxy sample*, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **470** (2017) 2617.
- [4] S. Nadathur, W. J. Percival, F. Beutler and H. A. Winther, *Testing low-redshift cosmic acceleration with large-scale structure*, *Physical review letters* **124** (2020) 221301.
- [5] T. Abbott, F. B. Abdalla, A. Alarcon, J. Aleksić, S. Allam, S. Allen et al., *Dark energy survey year 1 results: Cosmological constraints from galaxy clustering and weak lensing*, *Physical Review D* **98** (2018) 043526.
- [6] T. Padmanabhan, *Cosmological constant—the weight of the vacuum*, *Physics Reports* **380** (2003) 235.
- [7] E. J. Copeland, M. Sami and S. Tsujikawa, *Dynamics of dark energy*, *International Journal of Modern Physics D* **15** (2006) 1753.

- [8] D. Huterer and D. L. Shafer, *Dark energy two decades after: observables, probes, consistency tests*, *Reports on Progress in Physics* **81** (2017) 016901.
- [9] M. Ishak, *Testing general relativity in cosmology*, *Living Reviews in Relativity* **22** (2019) 1.
- [10] N. Aghanim, Y. Akrami, M. Ashdown, J. Aumont, C. Baccigalupi, M. Ballardini et al., *Planck 2018 results-vi. cosmological parameters*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics* **641** (2020) A6.
- [11] L. Verde, T. Treu and A. G. Riess, *Tensions between the early and late universe*, 2019.
- [12] B. Bassett and R. Hlozek, *Baryon acoustic oscillations, Dark energy: observational and theoretical approaches* (2010) 246.
- [13] P. A. Abell, J. Allison, S. F. Anderson, J. R. Andrew, J. R. P. Angel, L. Armus et al., *Lsst science book, version 2.0, arXiv preprint arXiv:0912.0201* (2009) .
- [14] S. Alam, M. Aubert, S. Avila, C. Balland, J. E. Bautista, M. A. Bershadsky et al., *Completed sdss-iv extended baryon oscillation spectroscopic survey: Cosmological implications from two decades of spectroscopic surveys at the apache point observatory*, *Physical Review D* **103** (2021) 083533.
- [15] S.-g. Hwang, B. L’Huillier, R. E. Keeley, M. J. Jee and A. Shafieloo, *How to use gp: Effects of the mean function and hyperparameter selection on gaussian process regression*, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.15081* (2022) .
- [16] C. K. Williams, *Gaussian processes for machine learning*. MIT press, 2005.
- [17] M. Seikel, C. Clarkson and M. Smith, *Reconstruction of dark energy and expansion dynamics using gaussian processes*, *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics* **2012** (2012) 036.
- [18] T. Holsclaw, U. Alam, B. Sansó, H. Lee, K. Heitmann, S. Habib et al., *Nonparametric reconstruction of the dark energy equation of state from diverse data sets*, *Physical Review D* **84** (2011) 083501.
- [19] T. Holsclaw, U. Alam, B. Sanso, H. Lee, K. Heitmann, S. Habib et al., *Nonparametric dark energy reconstruction from supernova data*, *Physical Review Letters* **105** (2010) 241302.
- [20] X. Li and A. Shafieloo, *A simple phenomenological emergent dark energy model can resolve the hubble tension*, *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* **883** (2019) L3.
- [21] V. Sahni and A. Starobinsky, *Reconstructing dark energy*, *International Journal of Modern Physics D* **15** (2006) 2105.
- [22] A. Krishak and D. K. Hazra, *Gaussian process reconstruction of reionization history*, *The Astrophysical Journal* **922** (2021) 95.
- [23] R. Von Marttens, J. E. Gonzalez, J. Alcaniz, V. Marra and L. Casarini, *Model-independent reconstruction of dark sector interactions*, *Physical Review D* **104** (2021) 043515.
- [24] H. Zhan and L. Knox, *Baryon oscillations and consistency tests for photometrically determined redshifts of very faint galaxies*, *The Astrophysical Journal* **644** (2006) 663.
- [25] H. Zhan, L. Knox and J. A. Tyson, *Distance, growth factor, and dark energy constraints from photometric baryon acoustic oscillation and weak lensing measurements*, *The Astrophysical Journal* **690** (2008) 923.
- [26] A. Oliveros, M. A. Sabogal and M. A. Acero, *Barrow holographic dark energy with Granda-Oliveros cut-off*, *The European Physical Journal Plus* **137** (2022) .
- [27] D. Foreman-Mackey, D. W. Hogg, D. Lang and J. Goodman, *emcee: the mcmc hammer*, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* **125** (2013) 306.
- [28] A. Bonilla, S. Kumar and R. C. Nunes, *Measurements of h_0 and reconstruction of the dark energy properties from a model-independent joint analysis*, *The European Physical Journal C* **81** (2021) 1.